

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF COTTON RAW PRODUCTION

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Annotatsiya. Paxtachilik tarmog'ini rivojlantirish, eng avvalo, mamlakat oziq-ovqat strategiyasi yo'nalishlari talablarini bajarish va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, boshqa tomondan, paxtachilik tarmog'iga kiruvchi korxonalarining mavjud mehnat, yer, suv, moddiy va moliyaviy resurslaridan, mulk shakllaridan qat'iy nazar, ular o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlarni takomillashtirish asosida, oqilona foydalanish evaziga tarmoq samaradorligini oshirish muhim hisoblanadi.

Аннотация. Развитие хлопчатобумажной промышленности служит, прежде всего, выполнению требований направлений продовольственной стратегии страны и обеспечению продовольственной безопасности. Также с другой стороны, важно повысить эффективность работы отрасли за счет рационального использования имеющихся трудовых, земельных, водных, материальных и финансовых ресурсов предприятий, входящих в хлопковую отрасль, независимо от форм собственности, на основе улучшения экономических отношений между ними.

Abstract. The development of the cotton industry, first of all, serves to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and ensure food security. Also, on the other hand, it is important to improve the efficiency of the network based on the rational use of the existing labor, land, water, material and financial resources of the enterprises that are part of the cotton industry, regardless of the forms of ownership.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy samaradorlik, rentabellik, asosiy ko'rsatkichlar, tizim, foyda, moddiy xarajat, daromad, ekin maydoni, yalpi mahsulot, xosildorlik, sof foyda, paxta tolasi, moliyaviy mablag'lar.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность, рентабельность, основные показатели, система, преимущества, материальные затраты, доход, посевная площадь, валовой продукт, урожайность, чистая прибыль, хлопковое волокно, финансовые фонды.

Keywords: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, system, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, productivity, net profit, cotton fiber, financial resources.

Researching the economic efficiency of cotton farming and scientifically studying the methodological basis of its evaluation is important in the development of the industry. In the process of studying the economic efficiency of any industry, it is necessary to differentiate between the concepts of "effectiveness", "efficiency" and "economic efficiency".

Research on increasing economic efficiency as a general economic problem has been studied by a number of theoretical and practical scientists of our country.

Efficiency in agricultural production is represented by indicators of social, economic and environmental efficiency, and these indicators are mutually different and interrelated.

Economic efficiency is based on the formation of the final result, i.e. profit, at the expense of increasing the production of products with less labor and material costs, without having a negative impact on the environment and ecological balance. And this ensures "social efficiency" in the end, when the product production is mutually compatible with the interests of the producers and members of the society.

From a theoretical and practical point of view, the concepts of "criterion" and "indicator" are widely used in the assessment of economic efficiency. "Meson" is derived from the Greek word "criterion" which means "judgment". The criterion is used as a means of evaluating and comparing the results of activities in the process of social production. "Indicator" is a concept that reflects certain aspects of performance evaluation.

Harmonic harmony of economic efficiency indicators justifies the need for comprehensive use of the system of indicators in assessing the economic efficiency of cotton farming. Because natural, value and relative indicators have their own characteristics in the assessment of economic efficiency. In particular, features such as full accounting of the crop grown in cotton farming, the possibility of accounting for the labor spent on growing cotton raw materials, making the calculations understandable for cotton growers, demonstrate the need for natural indicators, and the income of cotton growers is created and accounted for. This causes the need for value indicators and indicators that replace indicators such as profitability and quality of cotton raw materials in the assessment of economic efficiency, respectively. Based on the unique features of the system of indicators, when evaluating the economic efficiency of cotton farming, it is necessary to pay special attention to the indicators that are the primary basis for economic efficiency and are compatible with the requirements of the market economy oriented towards social relations, and it is appropriate to look at them in terms of "key indicators". These indicators are reflected below:

- cotton yield calculated on the basis of cultivated areas,
- gross income calculated per employee, in sums;
- net profit per worker, in sums;
- monetary income of employees, in sums;
- rate of return, in percentage terms.

As mentioned above, productivity is the primary basis of the effectiveness of factors affecting the economic efficiency of cotton farming. The extent to which the economic indicators determining economic efficiency are formed depends on productivity. Higher productivity increases gross output in terms of natural or value, which affects gross income, profit and profitability indicators. If we evaluate from this point of view, we understand that productivity is one of the main indicators that determine economic efficiency.

According to its characteristics, gross income is an economic indicator that fully reflects economic efficiency. Because it reflects the profit and wages achieved in cotton farming. Different proportions of these two indicators have an impact on the socio-economic importance of gross income. In particular, the high profit ratio in the gross income ensures the growth of economic efficiency, but it cannot fully reflect the material interests of cotton growers. In this case, material interest is determined by the ratio of wages in gross income at

an acceptable level. On this basis, the ratio of profit and salary in gross income creates two different situations. The first situation shows high efficiency and wages below the level of demand, and the second situation is based on the fact that efficiency is low, but wages are at the level of demand.

In order to achieve the first situation, cotton farms increase the net income by reducing the wages of cotton growers. This, firstly, has a negative impact on the attitude of cotton growers to work, and secondly, it leads to a violation of the requirements of the market economy, which is oriented towards social relations. On this basis, it is necessary to pay proper attention to both ratios when taking into account the gross income of cotton farms. The above-mentioned features are the basis for considering the ratio of gross income to cultivated areas as an indicator that fully reflects economic efficiency in cotton farming.

Net profit is a value indicator that determines the seasonal final annual result of cotton growers. The distribution of profit achieved in cotton farming largely determines its social importance. In this respect, profit is of particular importance in various forms of economic management. In this matter, the distribution of profits in the company and farms is proof of our opinion. A part of the profit is given to the cotton growers in the company's farms in the form of dividends, and the rest is used for the specified purposes. In the case of a farm, there is no specific distribution of profit, the farmer decides this issue himself. If we take into account the need for the profit achieved in cotton farming to directly serve the needs of cotton growers in the conditions of a market economy oriented towards social relations, we can see that the ratio of profit per worker is one of the main indicators that determine the economic efficiency of cotton farming. Also, profit is used as a basis for determining the profitability of production in cotton farming.

Profitability is considered as one of the main indicators of economic efficiency of cotton farming, and it represents the profit obtained at the expense of one soum spent on cotton farming. Profitability, by its nature, makes it possible to assess the potential of the network on the basis of making a final, general conclusion about the economic efficiency of the network. This justifies the fact that the level of profitability depends on the cost of the product as well as on the profit. The cost of the product consists of the money spent on its production, material costs and wages. In order to increase profitability at the expense of cost reduction, cases of reducing wages in the cost structure lead to the violation of the system of material interests in the conditions of the transition to the market economy. In this respect, ensuring the acceptability of these two ratios in the cost structure is the main requirement of the market economy. If we evaluate the above-mentioned indicators from the point of view of material interest, each of them reflects some aspects of economic efficiency, as well as implies material interest at the end of the season. However, meeting the needs of cotton growers during the season is also an important necessity. This necessity is solved by income in the form of nature and value. In cotton farming, the indicator that fully reflects the level of providing cotton growers with wages is the amount of cash income per worker. This indicator is based on the recalculation of the ratio of the net profit from cotton production to the number of employees according to the months of the season. Considering this indicator in cotton farming, firstly, it allows to determine the condition of meeting the daily needs of cotton growers and to determine measures to improve it based on this, secondly, it helps to improve the attitude of cotton growers to property and work, and thirdly, it improves the

social condition and standard of living of cotton growers. the ground is created for improvement.

CONCLUSION

1. The development of the cotton growing complex, which is of crucial importance for the country's economy in modern economic conditions, gives a strong impetus to the development of raw material production and industrial sectors. This is also evident in the experience of developed countries. From this point of view, encouraging the development of the cotton complex and increasing its competitiveness is important for the national economic interests of our country. Support for the development of the cotton complex can become the basis for the development of other structural complexes of the national economy.

2. Increasing economic efficiency in cotton farming is related to the following factors:

- the requirement of fertile, flat land for cotton cultivation and the necessity of strict adherence to the agrotechnology of cotton cultivation, feeding, watering and processing;
- elimination of seasonality in the organization of labor and provision of labor resources with even and full employment throughout the year;
- changes in the demand for cotton fiber in the world market, the need to harvest cotton in a short period of time, etc.
- determination of the ratio of organic and mineral fertilizers necessary for the implementation of agrotechnical activities, timely completion of irrigation works according to the established standards, as well as the selection of fruitful, promising cotton varieties resistant to various diseases in the cross-section of regions placement;
- to achieve proportionality of the amount of financial resources and the prices of infrastructures in farms and to take measures to ensure cost savings for cotton care;
- increasing labor productivity by improving the qualification and retraining of specialist employees, workers and employees, using the mechanism of financial incentives for them;
- to ensure effective use of drip or interrow irrigation methods in the conditions of increasing water scarcity.

3. As a result of the research, indicators representing the efficiency of cotton cultivation were systematized. These indicators allow to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of all types of resources in the field, covering the relevant macroeconomic indicators. As a result of the implemented measures, it is necessary to express the production economic efficiency of the farm in the form of natural, value, relative and quality indicators.

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